

The Cross-Reality Lab Usability Playbook

73 Guidelines to Survive Cross-Reality Lab Usability

CROSS Lab

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The checklist to which this playbook is a supplement can be found on [Zenodo](#).

Process

Product: Playbook & Checklist - 73 Guidelines

Usability starts at the very first point of the interaction – when a user initially accesses your laboratory.

If the login process is convoluted or unclear, this first impression can negatively influence the entire user experience. Importantly, "connection" refers not only to the login procedure itself, but also to general issues of connectivity and system availability that users may encounter.

1 - 1 Connecting to Laboratory

 Users can access the laboratory at any time (if possible)

Make sure that experiments and examples are running and available.

Some people rather work at night. Others in the early mornings.

The system status has to be clear. As well as the status of experiments, apparatuses and devices.

Ensuring good availability of time slots is essential.

1 - 2 Connecting to Laboratory

Users can access the laboratory from anywhere (if possible)

Cross Reality Labs are designed to be highly available, with a particular focus on accessibility for people with disabilities. Please ensure that their specific access needs are taken into account, including support for users of assistive technologies.

Make sure that the user can work using different end devices (screen resolutions, navigation with and without keyboard, touch screen).

Most frequently used screen resolutions worldwide (<https://gs.statcounter.com/>)

Are requirements of the lab fulfilled by normal end user devices? Avoid non-standard software. You should support at least Chromium-based web browsers as those count for 70% of website visits.

Most frequently used browsers (<https://gs.statcounter.com/>)

1 - 3 Connecting to Laboratory

For experiments with exchangeable components: laboratory systems make clear which combinations are valid

If students are new to the topic, ensure they understand which combinations are valid and which are not — and explain the reasoning behind each case.

Invalid apparatus combinations must be visualized differently from unavailable devices, so that learners can clearly distinguish between them.

If a device is reserved by another person, make sure that this information is available.

1 - 4 Connecting to Laboratory

 Lab systems make clear which experiments are available and when

Users are familiar with daily/weekly/monthly planner views.

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
		1	2 	3	4	5
6	7	8 	9	10	11	12
13	14	15	16	17	18 	19
20	21	22	23	24	25	26

If you mark the status of a system or device, make sure the people are familiar with the marking. For example, the colors of a traffic light are almost always known and understood.

You might want to display alternatives if an experiment is not available, e. g., show a simulated experiment instead of a physical experiment or show an experiment with slightly different equipment.

1 - 6 Connecting to Laboratory

 Users can access the laboratory easily, e.g. easy login and clear login data

Make sure every user has the complete login information they need. Especially if there are users from different universities some may have a username, some a (student) number and so on.

Make sure that the user knows which is the login name.

Make sure there is an easy way to reset/recover login information.

Ensure that each user from any possible language/cultural background can handle this site.

The image shows a login form for 'CROSS Lab'. The form includes a 'Username' input field, a 'Password' input field, a blue 'Log in' button, a 'Lost password?' link, a section for 'Some courses may allow guest access' with an 'Access as a guest' button, a language dropdown menu set to 'English (en)', and a 'Cookies notice' button. Green arrows point from the text on the left to these specific elements: the 'Username' field, the 'Log in' button, the 'Lost password?' link, and the language dropdown.

Offer the possibility to delete the account.

Make sure that the login status is clear.

Ensure that the login/logout field is easy to find.

Use encrypted communication only (HTTPS).

Offer single sign on if possible. Think about password-less login.

The usability and user experience of a (remote) experiment may suffer through technical decisions made in creating them.

Problems might arise when they can only interact with a stuttering interface where visuals are hard to recognize and details get lost in the representation.

Additionally, the experiment suffers if a user has to wait a long time for any action to have an observable effect or the user is unexpectedly disconnected due to a timeout that he has not been warned about.

2 - 1 Technical Quality

Users can trust the technology of the laboratory to work

Ensure the availability and continuity of the experiments.

Avoid experiments that need manual handling. For such cases: Are simulations or ultra-concurrent labs possible?

Ensure that the user cannot break the experiment. This is a big difference to on-site-labs where breaking an experiment might be part of the learning process.

2 - 2 Technical Quality

Users experience high visual quality

Provide artificial lighting for the experiment.

If your setup involves moving devices, make sure the camera operates at a high enough frame rate.
For smooth motion, aim for at least 30 frames per second.

Employ high resolution cameras or videos but keep usual screen resolutions in mind (see also [Playbook Item 1.2](#)).

Ensure that the camera shows the necessary lab equipment only.

Examples

Artificial lighting

High contrast

High resolution camera

Few compression artifacts

No distracting objects

When having moving devices, ensure that the device is visible anytime due to lighting constraints or contrast issue.

2 - 3/4 Technical Quality

- Users experience low start up time (e.g., heat-up times, website load times, experiment set-up)
- Users experience low waiting times between different steps of the experiment

If loading a website took longer than a few seconds, you should present the loading status.

Loading...

Minimize website loading time by optimizing images and videos (reasonable resolution, compression).

Avoid slow-running experiments such as some (bio-)chemical processes. For such cases: Are simulations or ultra-concurrent labs possible?

When visualizing measurement values, minimize the amount of data on server side (e.g., render plots in browser to reduce server load).

2 - 5 Technical Quality

Users experience low latency

High latency might distract users and may cause nausea in some situations.

Experiments may fail if the video/input lags.

Low latency is especially important for virtual reality/ augmented reality experiments to improve the VR/AR experience.

[OpenSpeedTest](#) is an open-source software application designed to measure network performance metrics.

Acceptable for voice over IP applications:
Ping < 400 ms
Jitter < 30ms

Digital twin of a UR5e collaborative robot in a virtual environment ([model of robot by Universal Robots A/S](#))

Deep Dive

ITU defines some transmission times (e. g. one way transmission in voice scenarios) in [ITU-T G.114](#)

2 – 6 Technical Quality

Users are notified of timeouts.

... and are provided with possible options for action, e. g.:

- extra time
- save current state
- alternative server systems

...

Make sure, that the user can adapt the system (and the speed) to its capabilities, e. g.:

- change resolution or compression of videos
- reduce number or accuracy of measurements

Try to avoid timeouts.

Communicate timeouts transparently.

3 Interaction Modes

The way that users interact with a laboratory plays a pivotal role in the usability of a laboratory.

No matter how well the interaction design was planned – if users are unable to operate the laboratory effectively, the interaction fails. This includes consideration of various input methods (e.g., not all users have access to a PC; some rely solely on smartphones), the degree of individual configurability, input mechanisms such as search fields or forms, potential media discontinuities, and future technological developments.

3 - 1 Interaction Mode

Lab providers anticipate how students may interact with the laboratory in the future (including different end-user devices)

Future devices might have different screen sizes, screen aspect ratios or resolutions.

Think about future technologies which might get widespread such as virtual reality, augmented reality, and large language models, but also technologies such as electronic paper.

Mobile usage might increase, which brings in many new challenges, such as a noisy environment.

Media preferences of users might change. Think about media formats podcasts, short-form content videos. Maybe we will have holograms in the future.

Deep Dive

Consider that common means of input might change over time – as seen in [the historic documents of Scotty inventing transparent aluminum](#).

3 – 2 Interaction Modes

Lab providers make different input methods available

Input controllers might be:

- speech,
- (gaming) controller,
- touch screen,
- hand gestures,
- eye tracking ...

Think about people with disabilities, they might require special input controllers.

Screens as input devices are tricky. Screen sizes and orientation might change during usage, different screen resolutions might make input objects (e.g., buttons) too small. See also

<https://www.nngroup.com/articles/mouse-vs-fingers-input-device/>

Different users might prefer different input methods.

Some input methods require prior knowledge, e. g., moving an avatar using the keys 'w', 'a', 's' and 'd' is not intuitive unless a user plays video games on PC.

Think about common guidelines when designing your laboratories, e.g., <https://www.justinmind.com/blog/button-design-websites-mobile-apps/>

Deep Dive

A (brief) lesson on buttons: [Button design for websites and mobile apps](#) .

3 - 3 Interaction Modes

Users can pause, resume, cancel experiments

Emergencies happen (e.g., children might need attention in home office, users need to use the toilet, and motion sickness may force users to take a break).

Users will only use pause, resume and cancel if they do not need to fear negative consequences.

Users might have different learning speeds / execution speeds and want to take a break.

Users might want to repeat a section (e.g., for better understanding) without repeating the whole experiment.

3 - 4 Interaction Modes

Users can magnify visual elements

Make sure that the visible elements are not “jumping around” with magnification.

If you use cameras, ensure a high enough quality that the image is still good under magnification.

Do parts of your layout disappear under magnification? Are all elements visible / clickable?

Users might want to magnify elements even in immersive virtual reality / augmented reality. At the moment, there does not seem to be a standard solution.

On many devices, it is out of your control if users use different magnification tools. This means that you should prepare your laboratory for that case.

3 – 5 Interaction Modes

Lab providers facilitate means of communication between users, esp. voice chat

Users seem to prefer voice chat to other communication methods, e.g., see Deep Dive

Give users the possibility to share what they currently see. Maybe even give peers the possibility to control the experiment (after consent by the original user).

Think about privacy. What happens if the spouse of the user runs through the camera in the nude? What happens if a child reads the number of a credit card while a user is in voice chat?

If you do not provide a communication channel, users will choose one that you cannot control.

Deep Dive

J. E. Ashby, "[The effectiveness of collaborative technologies in remote lab delivery systems](#)," 2008 38th Annual Frontiers in Education Conference, Saratoga Springs, NY, USA, 2008, pp. F4E-7-F4E-12.

3 – 6 Interaction Modes

If the content of the experiment is individualized based on user: Users should be able to access the non-individualized version

One of the basic principles in design is controllability. By being able to access a non-individualized version, we allow the user to be in control.

Individualization might lead to discrimination. For example, using individualized data for user profiling might lead to overly leaning into stereotypes (e.g., if a person has no academic parents, they might be prognosed with a higher chance of failure).

Bad individualization might lead to design with bad ethics: [The Role of Design Ethics in UX](#)

Deep Dive

A Primer on Terminology and Way-of-Thinking: [Customization vs. Personalization in the User Experience](#)

3 - 7 Interaction Modes

Lab providers supply supportive search tools

Users will most likely look for an input box at the top. Your search should be there.

Think about the robustness of your search. Users might make typos or use a wrong word.

Make suggestions for searches once the user starts typing.

Provide a sitemap in addition to search functionality.

Deep Dive

Make your [Search Visible and Simple](#)

3 – 8 Interaction Modes

Lab systems provide navigation that follows user needs (e.g., website flow, menu on machines), including means to backtrack

This relates to the basic principle of conformance to expectations: Users bring in expectations from other (similar) systems they use so you should follow those expectations. A good example is the undo action, which users are expecting to be either CTRL-Z (Windows, Linux) or ⌘Z (Apple).

This touches on the basic principle of robustness against user errors: Users want a system that they can use without the fear of harming a person or damaging the system.

[You are not the user.](#) What a user needs and where a user looks might be entirely different than where you as a laboratory developer / educator might want and look.

Do not ask the user how something should be designed. Only ask them where problems are and what features they want. [Users are not designers.](#)

Deep Dive

Stop Counting Clicks: [The 3 Click Rule is Nonsense](#)

3 – 9+ Interaction Modes

- ✓ Lab systems provide means to tackle every task without leaving the system
- ✓ Educators adapt the tasks such that students do not need to leave the (digital) system
- ✓ Lab providers avoid media discontinuity – that is, switching between different kinds of media

Tutorials and other helpful/supporting materials should be included in the laboratory.

Think about how the task (sheet) could be embedded in the laboratory.

Also think about communication (see [Playbook Item 3.5](#)).

Make it clear when an action makes the user leave the system, e.g., clearly mark external links.

All data which is needed should be accessible within the laboratory. Import / export should be minimized (e.g. only for the final report). Data visualization should be part of the laboratory. If data must be processed, this should be possible inside the laboratory.

3 - 12 Interaction Modes

Lab providers separate variable experiment parameters and user preferences

Observe where users expect to find an option. They might look for it in a different place than you would.

Users might not want to start an experiment just to change settings for experiments.

Make clear which options affect what exactly. For example, does an option called “brightness” change a single experiment, all experiments, or the entire laboratory system?

Provide clear descriptions for each option. For example, “temperature” is vague, whereas “temperature of the oven” is more specific and informative.

Use sensible default options. Test and measure (not ask) what users prefer.

See also [Playbook Item 3.15](#).

3 – 13 Interaction Modes

Lab systems provide input validation, placeholders, and clear labels for user input

Input validation:

- Do not be too strict. Give the user the possibility to experiment with different values.
- Use helpful error messages. Include actions a user can do in an error message.
- Be aware of and handle local conventions (e.g., the meaning of . and , in numbers is different in different countries).

Placeholders:

- Still show placeholders when values are entered, especially if they contain important information.
- Be careful with jargon, users might not remember / know the terms.

Labels:

- Be careful with jargon, users might not remember / know the terms.
- By clicking on the labels, users should get to the associated input field.
- Always make it clear which unit should be input (e.g. "speed (m/s)").

 m/s

3 - 14 Interaction Modes

Users can adjust the execution speed of the experiment, up to step-by-step execution, if possible

Think about both directions: Making experiments faster & slower.

Always display clearly to the user which execution speed the experiment currently has.

Make clear when important stuff is happening, so users won't skip it.

This might not be possible (at all) when the real world is involved, but even there try to make unnecessary busywork skippable. If there is a lot of busywork or waiting, maybe another form (ultra-concurrent lab, simulation) is more suitable.

3 – 15 Interaction Modes

Lab systems provide shortcuts for more experienced users but hide them from inexperienced users

The fastest way is not always the easiest to understand.

Beginners might be overwhelmed by too many options, but experienced users might want more control or more options to experiment.

Deep Dive

Shortcuts — hidden from novice users — may speed up the interaction for the expert user: [Jakob's Heuristic #7 - Flexibility and Efficiency of Use](#)

3 – 16 Interaction Modes

 Lab providers anticipate required motoric skills / sensitivity to operate devices for input and output, esp. for VR

Regarding accessibility: Think about people with little strength, mobility or (hand) precision. They should also be able to operate the laboratory. Some users might even depend on voice input.

Especially for VR, AR and touch: Think about making the sensitivity of the input configurable.

Different input devices have different precision. For example, a game controller has precise relative movement, but bad absolute movement.

Especially for VR, AR and touch: Make “physical” objects you interact with large enough.

One possibility might be a scalable interface so that the size of input elements can be increased.

You can't smell a virtual laboratory (yet).

Still, the more immersed a user can get into the experimental environment, the more the environment can facilitate both learning as well as conducting experiments in general. A virtual or remote laboratory should thus strive to reflect the real experiment as closely as possible and with as much freedom for the user as feasible. At the same time, it should scaffold users according to their needs – this is where the additional layer of technology can excel compared to traditional laboratories, especially in learning environments. Throughout all this, however, care should be taken to utilize prior experience of the users (e.g., with regards to interface design or tool functionality) and to always provide a fast method of exit.

4 - 1 Immersion

Lab providers design the laboratory as close to reality as feasible

Avoid a mismatch between (virtual) avatars and their environment (e.g., do you really need a cartoon bunny in a factory line?).

Ensure that virtual/simulated processes closely mimic the actual lab design.

Construct your virtual/simulated apparatuses as closely to reality as possible (e.g., with regards to button layout/interface design).

For VR/AR applications, special care needs to be taken that tracked body parts (e.g., the hand) move as they do in reality.

More realistic

4 - 2 Immersion

Lab systems provide feasible degrees of freedom

You don't need to offer *every* option/interface/... your devices provide but should offer *all* those a learner can be *reasonably* expected to (want to) interact with.

Provide a "standard" mode with reduced functionality and an "expert" mode with more in-depth features and shortcuts through the lab (see also [Playbook Item 3.15](#)).

You don't need to make every possible parameter for every possible action available – reduction, where feasible and sensible, is okay, too.

Having the option to play around with system configurations fosters student insight by providing exploratory learning experience.

4 - 3 Immersion

Lab providers design functionality in adherence to the learned expectations of the user

Don't make "magic" happen to hide processes and system reactions from the users they would be able to see normally (in a "real" system).

Ensure that every moving part and interaction plays out as it would normally (in a "real" system).

Stay with established rules – water flows through the lower half of the pipe, the square button doesn't start media playback, red means "stop".

Keep usual and established usage patterns in mind (e.g., don't move "Copy" to a different shortcut than "CTRL+C"/"⌘C" and afterwards bind another function to that shortcut; keep the "exit" button in the top right corner).

Deep Dive

Users should not have to wonder whether different words, situations, or actions mean the same thing. Follow platform conventions: [Jakob's Heuristic #4 - Consistency and Standards](#)

4 - 4 Immersion

Users have ways to quickly leave the laboratory

Mark any and all "exits" clearly.

Properly handle external exits (Window closes/Alt+F4, software crashes, PC shutdowns).

Don't bog the user down with forms/surveys and too many confirmation dialogues on their way out.

Differentiate different exit types (e.g., "save and quit" vs. "abort").

Be mindful of user situations outside of their (or your) control – e.g., situations triggered by children or pets, or a burning stove.

Be mindful of the user's mental state (panic attacks, cognitive load, etc.)

Deep Dive

Users often perform actions by mistake. They need a clearly marked "emergency exit" to leave the unwanted action: [Jakob's Heuristic #3 – User Control und Freedom](#)

5

Feedback to Users

User actions should not disappear into the void, and the user should always have a grasp on what is happening around them.

This also extends to virtual or simulated spaces. Thus, every action should trigger an observable reaction. Wherever feasible, user should provide with additional details and status information to help them orient themselves. Errors and failure states should be clearly communicated in a form the user can make sense of, and if anything goes awry and the user does not feel they can recover from there on their own, they should be able to seek help – just as they would in a physical laboratory.

This is especially relevant for learners, where early and accurate feedback can facilitate learnings.

5 – 1 Feedback to Users

Lab systems provide sufficient feedback for user actions

Highlight buttons when they are pressed
– highlight any interactable element while it is being interacted with.

Give visual indicators of successful & failed actions.

Highlight possible next steps or hide impossible actions.

Give hints as to *why* something failed; don't just say "oops, something went wrong".

Tell users about the progress they just made ("you completed step 8/11"; "you are 42% done").

Provide (configurable) multi-modal feedback (e.g., different sounds for different actions; haptic feedback)

Make feedback evident and clearly visible, but not obtrusive. A banner at the top of the visual frame which says "Success!" is okay, a pop-up which locks the other elements is not (except when it provides crucial information for the next steps, but even then, allow expert users to skip it – see also [Playbook Item 3.15](#)).

Deep Dive

Harley, A. (2018, June 3). [Visibility of system status \(usability heuristic #1\)](#). Nielsen Norman Group.

5 - 2 Feedback to Users

Lab systems offer supplementary material where it benefits the user

Include helpful information in tooltips.

Observe where users look for help. It might be different than where you look for help.

Provide references and links for further reading.

Weave relevant explanations in when and where they are needed.

Deep Dive

It's best if the design doesn't need any additional explanation. However, it may be necessary to provide documentation to help users complete their tasks: [Jacob's Heuristic #10 - Help and Documentation](#)

5 – 3 Feedback to Users

Lab systems provide users with easy-to-access means to contact staff

Offer some “shout for help” feature from within an experiment.

Always offer direct and unobstructed communication to a human, do not hide this behind walls (e.g., do not only offer AI chatbots, do not hide the contact e-mail somewhere in the third layer of the help section).

Provide contact info for educators & tech support in obvious, easy to reach places.

Make it easy to ask questions and file error reports (see also [Playbook Item 5.5](#)). This includes both accessibility and low hurdles for the user to overcome (no long-winded forms, forms that are easy to understand and complete, means of communication that are easy to find, welcoming and supportive language) as well as easy means for users to fill out details from their specific context (e.g., a specific scenario ID for questions regarding content or a specific incident ID for a bug report which help the other side to identify the problem).

5 - 4 Feedback to Users

Lab systems provide the users ways to undo unwanted actions

Provide a "roll back" or "reload checkpoint" feature.

Implement standard undo actions (e.g., CTRL-Z / ⌘Z) (see also [Playbook Item 3.8](#)).

Warn the user when they approach a "point of no return", e.g., aborting the experiment or entering the next phase of the experiment.

5 - 5 Feedback to Users

Lab systems display understandable information about errors to users (e.g., no error code, no stack trace)

Display useful error messages. "Error 43105" is not helpful. Answer the following questions:

What caused the user (no stack trace or technical information, but understandable to users)?

What can the user do now (even if it only is restart or contact the administrator)?

Assume the average user doesn't understand HTTP status codes and exception traces and their meaning in your specific context.

If you need technical details for troubleshooting / debugging, make it easy for users to report it (e.g., you could show the user an ID to include in a support ticket which can be mapped to a unique incident report in the back-end, or you could store important information in a QR code).

As with everything, lab providers and educators need to stay aware of applicable regulatory statutes, such as institutional policy or privacy law. Especially if a laboratory is offered internationally, this can quickly become a jungle of legal documents difficult to navigate and consolidate.

6 – 1/2 Rules and Regulations

- Lab providers provide a comprehensive privacy policy that is easy to find
- Lab providers state the owner / legal representative for the site clearly

List "terms of use", "privacy policy", and "legal notice"/"impressum" near each other in a place that stays constant, like a footer banner.

Provide a concise privacy policy that is factually correct but cleansed from "legalese" in addition to your formal policy.

Provide all terms, policies and legal information in plain language.

When a user needs to contact the legal representative, they probably already have an issue and are in some form of emotional distress. Provide an individual name as contact person instead of an entire office, department, or company to increase trust in and transparency of the communication and to humanize the correspondence.

6 – 3 Rules and Regulations

Lab providers allow for removal and correction of accounts or account data (as far as legally possible)

In general, it won't be detrimental to you to stay GDPR-compliant, even if you are positioned outside of the EU.

As indicated by the addendum of this item, make sure that you stay compliant with your legal obligations and organizational requirements regardless of the recommendations of this item.

If an individual account exists for a user, make a button to "delete this account" (see Art. 17 EU-GDPR) easy to find within the profile settings (similarly, a button to "send me what you know about me"; see Art. 15(3) EU-GDPR).

Where deletion is not possible (e.g., because grades must be kept by law) you must restrict the processing of data to strictly to legal claims, for protection of other people, or for important public interests (see Art. 18 GDPR).

Provide a venue for users to report errors in their data (e.g., misspelled name, erroneous lab scores) or to correct it themselves (where sensible – letting users edit lab scores is probably not a good idea).

Deep Dive

[GDPR](#), or "General Data Protection Regulation", is an EU-wide regulation governing data processing in the EU or concerning EU populace.

While up-to-date-ness seems only like a content problem, it severely impacts the satisfaction of use (and therefore the usability) as well as the user experience of the laboratory, since no-one wants to work with equipment or learn content that is outdated and not relevant anymore. However, not everything that is old is necessarily outdated.

7 - 1 Up-to-date-ness

Educators teach content that is relevant to the current discourse

Make sure your content is not superseded – except when the historical perspective is relevant for your context.

Just because something is new does not mean it is relevant; e.g., a newly developed programming language might be current but never gain relevance.

Even if content is old, it doesn't need to be outdated – e.g., backpropagation for neural networks and transformer models stem from the 1980s; even older still relevant concepts are, for example, classical mechanical principles like levers and leverage, the Pythagorean theorem, Pavlov's classical conditioning, classical music theory, Ohm's law, ... However, not all old content is relevant, e.g., Heliocentrism or the medical humor theory are both old and outdated.

You don't need to address the most recent "flavor" of a technology – just because someone developed a new engine with two additional cylinders doesn't mean you need to stop teaching 8-cylinder engines. In this case, it is more important to teach fundamentals, e.g., how combustion engines work (without discussing specific models) and how the number of cylinders generally relates to performance.

7 - 2 Up-to-date-ness

Lab providers use commonly used and/or state-of-the-art technology

Teach your students methods, models, and technology which will be useful for them to know in their work (and private) life.

Your users are comfortable with modern desktop UIs, mobile devices and touch interfaces. Don't force them to use DOS or a terminal interface if it isn't needed.

Don't force the user to use outdated technologies - this refers to hardware and software - except where you need the user to understand the historic relevance of something and how it relates to why things are the way they are now.

There might be technology which is outdated but still has wide adoption, e.g., older programming language versions still in use. Another example: steam locomotives are considered an outdated technology. However, they are still in use in certain places (where they can't be replaced) and their maintenance and new production still needs to be taught (though maybe only to a small number of students).

The way information is displayed has a huge effect on whether users can both navigate the system and find the information they want/need. Important concepts here are consistency, completeness of information, understandability, and making important information easy to find.

8 - 1 Information Display

Lab systems follow platform conventions

When the laboratory aligns with the system's conventions, users spend less mental effort. Familiar patterns make the experience smoother — so users can focus on their work, not the tool.

Conventions might be different for the different platforms you offer your laboratory on (e.g., CTRL-Z or ⌘Z). In that case, try to follow all of them and show the user proactively where you decided for one over another.

Lab systems should look and feel like systems the users already use, e.g.,

- for reservation use a date selection that looks like a digital calendar;
- for websites, a click on the logo should bring the user to the home page.

For newer platforms and technologies, there might not be any wide-spread conventions yet. In that case, it is imperative to have a good tutorial. Equally, if there are cases where you need to divert from conventions, you need to show the user explicitly where you diverted.

Lab systems should provide the same functionality as systems the users already use, e.g., for reservation offer serial reservation.

8 - 2 Information Display

Users receive information about their progress, goals, and context

The following information should be displayed at any time:

- Where am I?
- Where did I come from (and how can I get back there)?
- Where can I go now?

Always show users the task they have to fulfill.

Show users how much work is still remaining.

This Morning's TODOs:

Get Up

Brush
your
Teeth

Get
Dressed

Prepare
Coffee

Buy
Breakfast

Go to
Work

8 – 3 Information Display

Lab systems display information clearly

Communicate each important information in at least three ways, e.g., shape, color, text. Examples are stop signs or ambulances.

Think about users with concentration problems (e.g., ADHD) or sensory issues like epilepsy. Do you really need every animation / video autoplay / audio autoplay / pop-up?

Let users recognize the information rather than having to remember it.

Think about what happens if a user interacts with your system. For example, does touch input cover information? Do menus open and hide information once a user moves their mouse?

Think about users with color-blindness. [There are different types of color-blindness.](#)

All user interfaces should have identical or at least similar structure to reduce the mental model a user has to have and the strain on their cognitive load.

Some users might have less mental capacity. They cannot take in much information at the same time.

Deep Dive

Minimize the user's memory load by making elements, actions, and options visible. Avoid making users remember information: [Jakob's Heuristic #6 – Recognition Rather Than Recall](#)

8 - 4 Information Display

Lab systems use consistent positioning and display styles

Each object in the user interface should be easily identifiable by having signaling elements (e.g., emergency stop buttons - all have the same form and color).

Think about grouping similar elements. Do not group items together that are not similar.

Different items should look different, similar items should look similar.

Expert users might need a different user interface than novice users. See at a plane cockpit: This might be cluttered for new users, but experts can easily find the instruments on any plane (See also [Playbook Item 3.15](#)).

Think twice: Do you really need each object? Can objects be hidden for new users or placed under a disclosure widget, accordion or other widget?

Use a simple background and a high contrast for all important elements.

Deep Dive

The Gestalt principles – https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DwR0SZTBMTU&list=PLJOFJ3Ok_iduObD_9dHwiYp804

8 – 5 Information Display

Lab systems use consistent positioning and display styles

Consistent styling lowers the requirements for the mental model a user has to have by making the user remember just a single layout.

If users can move elements, they should

1. stay in the same place on each visit; and
2. stay in the same place across multiple sites.

Think about where your laboratory is embedded in. For example, if it is embedded in Moodle, it should be consistent with the Moodle style.

8 – 6 Information Display

Lab providers make important information easy to identify

Think about what colors can communicate. For example, red is communicating both danger and attention. Keep in mind that the associations with colors may differ in different cultures.

Be selective and careful: If everything is important, then nothing is important.

Important information should always be communicated in three ways. For one example, a stop sign communicates its message in text, color and shape. Another example are ambulances, which not only communicate using visual signals (brightly colored cars, blue lights) but also auditory signals (sirens). Consider using multiple different sensory signals where feasible to facilitate accessibility.

Avoid unnecessary content. Consider greying out or even hiding options that are not available.

8 – 7 Information Display

Lab providers sort information by importance

Users usually scan websites (and similar media) in different patterns (not just the more well-known F-shaped pattern). Thus, important content should be displayed according to these patterns. Keep in mind the difference between left-to-right and right-to-left reading.

For input fields: provide meaningful focus sequence orders.

Ask users which information they find important – it might be different from your own intuition.

Think about hiding unimportant information (e.g., Accordion) or make it visually less stimulating (e.g., reduce color saturation or grey out elements).

Structure text reasonably. Use the appropriate structure elements of your system (e.g., the correct HTML tags like `<h1>` for web-based laboratories).

Deep Dive

Nielson UX Slogan #5: [Brevity = Brilliance](#)

8 – 8 Information Display

Lab systems avoid the need to page-scroll, especially horizontally

Think about different screen sizes, e.g., use responsive design.

Be careful that no elements leave the screen, especially if scrolling is disabled.

Implement clicks or dragging for moving content instead of scroll bars (since these feel more natural). Make it clear how content can be moved. Ideally, movable elements can also be moved using only the keyboard.

8 – 9 Information Display

Lab systems display navigation elements prominently and consistently

Navigation in experiments should provide enough freedom, e.g., allow steps backwards where possible.

For the hamburger menu, the position top left is important for recognition.

Always show the navigation elements if possible. Rather use the space to display navigation than to confuse users.

The NNGroup provides a checklist for menus and navigation elements.

In small spaces, there are different methods for organizing navigation. The hamburger menu might be good for small spaces (only), but maybe another solution like tabs, top navigation bar or navigation hub might be preferable.

8 – 10 Information Display

Lab providers use high-contrast and barrier-free color schemes

There are [different types of colour-blindness](#) you should take into consideration.

Avoid distracting elements such as autoplay video/audio, blinking elements, moving elements or changing elements. They will especially impact users with concentration problems (such as attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder ADHD). Users should be able to disable any animation or multimedia using keyboard commands.

Text contrast according to WCAG 2.2:

- [Minimum ratio is 4,5:1 \(with some exceptions\)](#)
- [An even better ratio is 7:1 \(with some exceptions\)](#)
- [Non-Text according to WCAG: 1:3](#)
- [The definition of "ratio" can be found in the WCAG 2.2](#)

Avoid designs where color is the only differentiating element, e.g., for buttons with different option, use text or shape in addition to color to convey information.

Deep Dive

Some examples of good color schemes can be found at [ColorBrewer2](#). See also Nuñez, J. R., Anderton, C. R., & Renslow, R. S. (2018). [Optimizing colormaps with consideration for color vision deficiency to enable accurate interpretation of scientific data](#). PLOS ONE, 13(7), e0199239.

8 – 11 Information Display

Lab providers make text readable

Think about [who the target audience is and what they actually need and want](#).

Test if the text is easy to understand. Users will have different background knowledge than you. Depending on the target audience, you might want to use plain language.

Use structure in your text. Use sensible headlines and paragraphs.

[Be as concise \(and short\) as possible](#).

Be sure that the user can actually read the text. Make it large enough and use a simple font face.

Ensure consistent formats and font faces.

Deep Dive

There are [many more aspects](#) that make text actually readable.

8 - 12 Information Display

Lab providers show examples where it benefits the laboratory

Examples can support the user's understanding of the experiment. This also includes possible combinations of components (where the experiment is modular) and source code.

Make sure the example actually runs. It is a bad and demotivating experience if examples do not work. Keep them updated if the laboratory changes.

Try to make the examples available within the experiments, not only on separate pages/media. (See also [Playbook Items 3.9 - 3.11](#))

8 – 13 Information Display

Lab systems clearly display executable actions

Buttons, links, sliders, and other interactable elements should be clearly distinguishable from non-interactive elements (like text).

Users usually expect executable actions to look like they look in the default system style. This, of course, highly depends on which system they use (Windows/Mac/Linux/Android/iOS/something different)

Gray out (or otherwise clearly mark) actions that are currently not available. If actions are generally not available or not available over a longer period, hide them.

Display a warning if users do actions that cannot easily be undone, e.g., aborting an experiment. Try to avoid such actions. This is also true for actions which make a user leave the system.

8 – 14 Information Display

Lab providers adjust the use of jargon and acronyms with respect to the target audience's prior knowledge (if in doubt, avoid acronyms and jargon)

Test whether users actually can understand your text. Users have a different knowledge level and background than you.

Think about both expert and novice users. Expert users might prefer text with more jargon and abbreviations if (and only if) it makes the text more concise.

Do not rely on users knowing technical terms / jargon / acronyms even if you told them before. Users might

1. forget;
2. take longer to remember;
3. misremember.

The design should speak the users' language. Use words, phrases, and concepts familiar to the user, rather than internal jargon. See [Jakob's Heuristic #2 - Match between System and the Real World](#)

Give an option to quickly explain jargon and acronyms, for example by providing a glossary or using system capabilities (like an HTML <abbr> tag).

Deep Dive

Nielsen UX Slogan #17: [This Is Too Easy to Understand](#)

8 – 15 Information Display

✓ Lab systems only show information relevant to the current task

Test whether users actually understand your text. Users have a different knowledge level and background compared to you.

Testing understandability is especially important for users with disabilities (e.g., reduced mental models, but also for users which need a screen reader).

Show all information a user needs to understand what is happening, even if it is in the background. This way, no 'magic' is happening.

Novice and expert users have different needs. Novice users usually need more information, while expert users often do not want to read information they already know.

Too many options that are not selectable might irritate and annoy your users.

Deep Dive

This relates to the concept of [pedagogical reduction](#).

8 – 16 Information Display

Lab systems explain why actions are not possible

Display useful error messages. “Error 43105” is not helpful. Answer the following questions: What caused the error (no stack trace or technical information, but understandable to users)? What can the user do now (even if it only is restart or contact the administrator)?

This related to many interaction principles like explainability, controllability, learnability and robustness against errors.

Grey out impossible options so users do not need to try them. If they are generally not available or not available over a period, hide them.

Think about choosing an input option which does not allow for invalid inputs and clearly communicate input boundaries. For example, a slider limits the input values in comparison to a text field. A list of radio buttons shows the available options better than a text field.

To ensure the laboratory is accessible to the widest possible audience, established accessibility standards should be followed.

That way, you can ensure that the laboratory is available even to some groups which are often overlooked. This can be beneficial both in market competition and in classroom settings. Examples may be providing several languages but also ensuring compatibility with assistive technology like screen readers or providing subtitles or sign language alternatives where sensible.

9 – 1 Accessibility (A11y/Ally)

Lab providers offer necessary support for students with special needs

If you offer any video format, consider including an option to display sign language. For example, you could use an avatar that provides sign language “subtitles” or film a real person signing in sync with the audio. Sign language is the native language of many deaf individuals, and reading text often requires additional effort.

However, keep in mind that there is no single universal sign language—it is a diverse family of languages. The specific sign language(s) you need to support will depend on your target audience and context.

Consider individuals with reduced cognitive abilities. How can we support them effectively? Do they require manual assistance, more guidance for correct input, or simplified language?

Example

Some people find it hard to think or understand.
How can we help them?
Do they need someone to help them with tasks, more help with typing, or easier words?

It might be possible to add haptic feedback. For example, in a VR lab students might include a glove which vibrates with varying intensity based on where the student holds the hand (e.g., to signal collision with a virtual object). Similarly, touch devices might vibrate when a button is pressed to confirm the input

9 – 1 Accessibility (A11y/Ally)

Lab providers offer necessary support for students with special needs

Think about how your lab works with screen readers and Braille displays.

Think about input for users with less precision in their motor skills. (See 3.2)

As a further tip, you should avoid designs where color is the only differentiating element, e.g., also choose different line and marker styles for line plots.

Strive to make all visuals accessible for people with colour vision deficiencies (CVD). Be aware that there are several types of CVD. You might want to consider testing a greyscale version of your visuals for the occasional printout or old-school eBook reader. You can test different CVD profiles with, e.g., Firefox' Developer options (F12 > "Accessibility" > "Simulate") or with Adobe's color tool (color.adobe.com/de/create/color-accessibility).

Deep Dive

See [WCAG guidelines give examples on how \(web-based\) laboratories can be implemented taking special needs into consideration](#). The [NIH](#) provides some useful [information](#) on CVD in general.

See also Nuñez, J. R., Anderton, C. R., & Renslow, R. S. (2018). [Optimizing colormaps with consideration for color vision deficiency to enable accurate interpretation of scientific data](#). PLOS ONE, 13(7), e0199239.

9 – 2 Accessibility (A11y/Ally)

Lab systems provide alt-texts for non-text elements for screen readers

For web-based laboratories: Do all form fields have labels? And (where it makes sense) “autocomplete”-attributes in HTML? Screen readers will be able to work with them.

Do all pictures have a description and/or alt text? And what about recordings and videos?

Alt text should be descriptive, not vague. Decorative elements do not always need alt text as those may interrupt screen readers.

Does the image contain text? If so, it should be included in the alt-text.

Information should be presented in two ways, if it is important in three ways. Example: Stop signs communicate their message in text, colour and shape. Consider using different modes, e.g., visual and audio.

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9 – 3 Accessibility (A11y/Ally)

Lab providers ensure that accessibility plug-ins / applets work (test multiple)

Both Firefox and Chrome/Edge allow testing a website if there are accessibility problems. The tools can be found in the "web developers" area (usually F12).

Web Accessibility Plugins might be

- UserWay
- EqualWeb
- AccessiBe
- Wave /Web Accessibility Evaluation Tool)
- Axe DevTools

Learning Productivity Tools

- Grammarly for Dyslexia
- Microsoft Immersive Reader
- Firefox Reader View (not available on all web pages)

9 - 4 Accessibility (A11y/Ally)

Lab providers support all needed languages

Stay in one language, i.e., don't mix languages within the same text.

Make clear which language options are available. Flag symbols are not a good indicator (e.g., English is associated with different countries; Switzerland has four official languages).

Display clearly which language is chosen to the user and to the system.

Sign languages are languages, too (be aware that there are multiple sign languages).

Think about cultural differences. Different cultures might need a different presentation of content. See: [Website Design in High-Context Cultures like China](#)

Making changes later is in general more expensive than planning ahead. This is also true for changes regarding usability. Thus, lab providers should anticipate in which contexts their laboratory may be used and define the requirements accordingly, e.g., with regards to usability, accessibility, and user experience. Doing this early in the project facilitates both compliance and smooth integration of usability into the laboratory. However, lab providers should consider that they cannot realistically anticipate all user needs; thus, diverse groups representative of the target audience should be included in the usability testing.

10 – 1 Development Process

🔍 Lab providers plan for Usability/UX early in the design process

Usability/UX is something that is baked into a product, not slapped on top of it after the fact – you wouldn't first construct a railway network and then determine demand after the fact.

You don't need a final product for testing – using mock-ups (e.g., cardboard cutouts) might just do the trick.

It is easier to stick to a quality road map than to “fix” a system once it has been completed, so integrating usability/UX early will save you time and effort in the long run.

Often, a small number of test users is enough. [Although usability testing with more test users and diverse methods is a bit more sophisticated, only using 5 test users is enough in many cases.](#)

Deep Dive

For some inspiration, you can look at how [Google implemented rapid prototyping for their products.](#)

10 – 2 Development Process

Lab providers do usability testing with diverse test groups

Be aware that your background and expectations differ from those of your user groups:

You are not the user. - see Nielsen [UX Slogan #1: You ≠ User](#)

Be sure to include your intended target audience in testing your system.

Diversity extends to all groups – so also students of different disciplines, different age groups, etc. Be aware of possible variables in your target group and include all relevant constellations in your test.

Deep Dive

Nielsen UX Slogan #11: [If You're Not Checking, You're Guessing](#); Nielsen UX Slogan #15: [Show Me the Data](#)

10 – 3 Development Process

✓ Lab providers anticipate the context of use for the laboratory

Be aware of the environment in which your laboratory is used (business/noise, distractions, lighting, ...).

Make sure to support different (input) device types (e.g., PC, mobile, tablet, ...) as feasible (see also [Playbook Item 3.2](#)).

Think about ways to provide assistance to different user groups (e.g., shortcuts for expert users or tooltips for novice users).

Deep Dive

Nielsen UX Slogan #14: [It Depends](#)

To be actually useful to users, a laboratory must be designed with their perspectives and needs in mind.

It is thus imperative – both for lab providers and for educators – to establish the perspectives of their prospective target audiences and to respect these perspectives during development and provision of the laboratory, e.g., with regards to prior knowledge, attention span or cognitive load, and with typical user errors.

11 - 1 Perspective Shift

Lab providers anticipate needs and context of the target audience

Who is your (primary) target group – K-12, first-semester students, senior students, doctorates, non-formal education?

Are you targeting educational or professional settings? Professional settings might need more degrees of freedom but less explanations.

Do not assume what your target audience wants – ask them and test if they can work with your system. At the same time, [do not ask for specific design decision, since they are no designer.](#)

Consider relevant special needs. See section 9 “Accessibility” of the checklist / playbook for more information.

Can you assume homogenous prior knowledge, or do you have to account for heterogeneous prior knowledge? Can you assume and build upon any prior knowledge at all? See also [Playbook Item 8.14.](#)

Generally, address your users in a way they can understand. Just like most of your users (probably) won't speak Gaelic, be aware of what manner you need to address them with and what interface and interaction options you need to provide for your target group.

Deep Dive

For some inspiration, you Nielsen UX Slogan #11: [If You're Not Checking, You're Guessing](#)

Nielsen UX Slogan #13: [Design for Them Not for You](#)

11 - 2 Perspective Shift

Lab providers anticipate missing prior knowledge of the target audience

Be aware of how much basic concepts you can assume your target audience to possess.

You are not the user - what might seem trivial to you may not be trivial for your audience.

Provide tooltips with detailed help - but don't bog the user down with unskippable tutorials!

By constructivist world view, you need to link new knowledge to existing knowledge so learners can properly absorb the new insights and put them in the correct context.

Deep Dive

See also "expert blind spots": [Nathan, Koedinger, Alibali \(2001\) Expert Blind Spot: When Content Knowledge Eclipses Pedagogical Content Knowledge](#)

11 - 3 Perspective Shift

Lab providers reduce abstraction and make processes transparent to users

Show all information a user needs to understand what is happening, even if it is in the background. This way, no 'magic' is happening.

Anticipate the mental model a user might have of a given experiment and provide means to transport all relevant information with regards to that mental model.

Please keep in mind that some users have less capacity for mental models and thus face increased difficulties when dealing with additional layers of abstraction.

Where abstraction is beneficial, make clear what abstractions are used and why and how they relate to the experiment.

Deep Dive

See also: [Playbook Item 4.1](#).

11 - 4 Perspective Shift

 Educators anticipate learners' concentration and attention span, e.g., by allowing breaks or notifying when important things happen

Let users pause the experiment when they want or warn before they enter a section where pausing isn't possible.

If users need to wait for a process to finish, inform them how long they need to wait ("simulation done in 2 hours").

Provide a way to notify users who have left their device in the meantime.

Motivate why waiting times are required.

Motivate why an experiment takes a long time.

Research on Attention Span is divided:

Bradbury, N. (2016). [Attention span during lectures: 8 seconds, 10 minutes, or more?](#) *Advances in Physiology Education*, 40(4), 509–513.

Empirical data doesn't support short attention spans in lectures; student attention depends primarily on the teacher.

Bradbury, N. (2017). [Do Students Really Have an Inability to Concentrate During Lectures?](#) *Academic Medicine*, 92(4), 428–428.

No attention decline could be measured.

Deep Dive

Mills, K. I. (Host). (2023, February). [Why our attention spans are shrinking](#), with Gloria Mark, PhD (No. 225) [Audio podcast episode]. In Speaking of Psychology. American Psychological Association.

11 – 5 Perspective Shift

🔍 Educators design tasks in anticipation of learners' cognitive load

Don't offer more degrees of freedom than is necessary to accomplish the task. This is in tension with [Playbook Item 4.1](#), thus a balance has to be found here.

Avoid overwhelming novice users with too much information at once. Instead, guide them step by step and provide scaffolding so they have time to become familiar with individual components.

Be aware of your students' circumstances – they won't be able to handle a task that requires 30 hours of attention from them during a normal lecture week, neither physically nor mentally.

Be aware that it is more taxing to engage with entirely foreign material as compared to familiar topics.

Deep Dive

Lewin, D. (2018). [Toward a theory of pedagogical reduction: Selection, simplification, and generalization in an age of critical education](#). Educational Theory, 68(4-5), 495-512.

11 – 6 Perspective Shift

Lab providers eliminate unneeded workload

Make your system easy to access (no long-winded login sequence). See also [Playbook Item 1.6](#).

Make your system easy to navigate (clear interface, minimal click paths). See also [Playbook Item 3.8](#).

Don't make users search for a standard feature – e.g., don't put "add student to classroom" under the tab for "site settings".

Don't offer more degrees of freedom than necessary to accomplish the task. This is in tension with [Playbook Item 4.1](#), thus a balance has to be found here.

11 - 7 Perspective Shift

Lab providers anticipate typical user errors

What happens when a user clicks a button they are not supposed to click right now? What happens when a user terminates the connection unexpectedly? (or is terminated due to spotty internet). See also [Playbook Item 5.5](#).

Provide a way to deliver helpful information to users about WHY what they did was wrong.

Provide input validation to catch expectable errors - like a user entering "four" instead of 4 - but make such validation transparent! I.e., provide information why what the user input was wrong ("you can only enter whole numbers here").

Provide a way to undo unwanted actions.

Deep Dive

Good error messages are important, but the best designs carefully prevent problems from occurring in the first place: [Jakob's Heuristic #5 - Error Prevention](#)

11 - 8 Perspective Shift

Lab providers anticipate the needs of administrators/maintainers

Make it easy to update legal info and comply with legal requirements (e.g., easy to edit the legal notice/ impressum; easy-to-find management tools for GDPR requests).

Provide the necessary configuration options to integrate the system into a pre-existing environment (AD/LDAP, Shibboleth, Single Sign-on, network configuration/subdomains/paths, branding/corporate ID, ...).

Provide a streamlined deployment process ("plug-and-play").

Offer a way for administrators to recover log data even when the system is down, to figure out why it is down.

Provide an easy way to install updates.

Provide streamlined admin features (user and data management, system config).

Ask administrators what they need since they actually are a target audience.

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